

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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OF SPORTS GYMNASTICS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS AND ITS EFFECT ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract; This is the topic of sports gymnastics common physical education in the classes his place of lessons efficiency added contribution and of students physical development effect about analysis to do in the eye holds Gymnastics is one of the most popular types of sports and physical education. The impact of environmental factors, the rhythm of modern life, the constant presence of aggressive microorganisms in the environment weakens the health of schoolchildren. Therefore, it is very important to strengthen the body's defense in all available ways - through a balanced diet, timely treatment of various diseases, preventive measures aimed at strengthening the immune system, as well as physical activity.

Key words : physical education , sports gymnastics , students , development , healthy marriage style , exercises .

Enter

Physical education lessons education of the process indispensable part become their purpose students physical development , healthy marriage style formation and sports activities is interesting . Sports gymnastics physical education in their classes important role plays because it is not only physical skills develops , perhaps aesthetic and technical also increases abilities . This in the article of sports gymnastics physical education in the classes place and his education to the process effect wider will be lit. Physical education lessons every one of the student physical and mental in development important place holds In these lessons of sports different types , including sports gymnastics wide is used . Sports gymnastics of students actions coordination , strength , endurance , flexibility and another physical qualities to develop service does

Gymnastics is one of the most popular types of sports and physical education. The impact of environmental factors, the rhythm of modern life, the constant presence of aggressive microorganisms in the environment weakens the health of

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schoolchildren. Therefore, it is very important to strengthen the body's defense in all available ways - through a balanced diet, timely treatment of various diseases, preventive measures aimed at strengthening the immune system, as well as physical activity.

With the advent of computers, smartphones and other "devices" that facilitate the daily life of schoolchildren, the physical activity of schoolchildren has decreased dramatically even compared to the last decade.

This leads to a gradual decrease in the student's functional ability, weakening of his musculoskeletal system, changes in the work of internal organs - unfortunately, changes for the worse. Lack of movement and energy consumption leads to malfunctions in all systems (muscles, blood vessels, heart, respiratory organs) and the body as a whole and contributes to the emergence of various diseases. Therefore, the impact of sports on the student's health is very important. Physical education and sports sometimes become the only forms of physical activity available to a person, with the help of which a schoolchild's natural need for movement and physical exercise is satisfied.

The effect of movement on systems and organs. The musculoskeletal system is strengthened: the size and strength of muscles increases, the bones of the skeleton become resistant to stress. During training or gymnastics, oxygen supply to muscles improves, blood capillaries that are not used during rest are activated, and new blood vessels are formed; Under the influence of regular training, the chemical composition of muscle tissue changes: the content of energy substances in them increases, which leads to intensive metabolic processes, protein synthesis and the formation of new muscle cells. Systematic exercises prevent the development of diseases of support and movement organs such as osteochondrosis, herniated intervertebral discs, arthrosis, atherosclerosis and osteoporosis. The nervous system is strengthened and developed. This is due to the improvement of agility, speed and coordination of movements. Gymnastic training contributes to the continuous formation of new conditioned reflexes, which are strengthened and formed in successive rows. The body will have the ability to adapt to more complex loads and perform exercises more efficiently and economically to achieve the desired results. The speed of nervous processes increases: the brain learns to respond to stimuli faster and make the right decision.

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The work of the heart and blood vessels improves. The effect of gymnastics on the body of a schoolboy makes the heart and blood vessels stronger. Training forces all organs to work intensively. During exercise, the muscles need more blood supply, which forces the blood vessels and the heart to pump more oxygenated blood per unit of time. At rest, the heart pushes about 5 liters of blood into the aorta per minute: during exercise, this amount increases to 10 and 20 liters. The heart and blood vessels of a schoolboy engaged in gymnastics quickly get used to stress and quickly recover from it.

The work of the respiratory system improves. During physical activity, breathing becomes deeper and stronger due to the increase in oxygen demand of tissues and organs. The amount of air passing through the respiratory organs per minute increases from 8 liters at rest to 100 liters when doing recreational gymnastics. The vital capacity of the lungs also increases.

Immunity increases and blood composition improves. During regular training of schoolchildren, the number of red blood cells increases from 5 million cubic meters to 6 million, their task is to neutralize harmful factors entering the body. This is a direct evidence of the strengthening of the protective forces of sports - the ability to withstand adverse environmental conditions. Physically active schoolchildren are less likely to get sick, and if they are exposed to a bacterial or viral attack, they will overcome it faster.

Types of gymnastics:

- **fitness gymnastics:** This type of gymnastics got its name for a reason. The complex includes exercises that help develop and strengthen the musculoskeletal system. Training has a positive effect on the immune, nervous and cardiovascular systems. Classes are often held in schools, they are soft and aimed at general strengthening of the body; In sanatoriums, dispensaries and other rehabilitation and wellness centers, a complex of advanced exercises aimed at eliminating existing defects in the musculoskeletal system and other body systems is used.

There are several other types of fitness gymnastics:

Rhythmic. Used to strengthen the musculoskeletal system, a series of exercises are performed very quickly to rhythmic music. Therefore, this type is often used in cases where it is necessary to adjust the weight of children and make lessons useful and interesting.

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Power. It is rarely used for children's development, usually to correct existing back defects to strengthen the muscular frame. Among the exercises, exercises with dumbbells, kettlebells, expanders and additional weights prevail.

Hygienic. The main exercises used to tone, relax and relieve tension are muscle stretching; Hygienic developmental gymnastics for children is often used in physical education classes in schools.

General. Develops motor skills, training uses elements of jumping, running and stretching.

- Rhythmic gymnastics

This Olympic sport is amazing and beautiful, every movement of the athlete is a kind of art learned from a young age. Any sport is dangerous, and professional gymnastics is one of the first places among sportsmen's injuries. Therefore, it requires special concentration and dedication in training. Parents should not force them to go to training against their will, if he does not like gymnastics for children, it is better to listen to his opinion.

Sports, like health, are divided into several types:

Artistic. Here, gymnastic exercises are performed to music and are a mixture of dance and gymnastics. They demand from the athlete not only the technical correctness of the elements. In the competition, the judges evaluate the lightness and fluency of the performance, artistic skills, costumes and even the harmony of the performance, the appropriateness of the movements to the musical accompaniment. Rhythmic gymnastics is performed with a ball, ribbon, stick or hoop.

Acrobatics. The most difficult type of gymnastics, it requires a lot of work on the athlete's body. Here, the main elements are focused on maintaining balance both in the performance of various acrobatic stunts and on the apparatus. Can be single or group. This discipline should not be confused with circus acrobatics, which also belong to the category of gymnastics, but not sports.

Sports. It is also an Olympic sport and differs from rhythmic gymnastics and acrobatics in that the elements are performed using rings, poles and uneven bars.

- **Practical gymnastics** :- is a set of practical exercises aimed at the realization of certain goals and tasks. For example, a course of therapeutic exercises aimed at correcting posture is classified as applied. As with other types, there are variations:

Military. A complex of special physical exercises used to improve the skills of conscripts. They help develop the professional skills necessary for soldiers. For

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example, drill training, endurance, speed development, and quick obstacle course training. It is widely used in military schools for the development of children.

Professional. A set of exercises to develop narrow skills necessary for professional activity. For example, there is a special set of exercises for the development of fine motor skills of the hands, which are necessary for surgeons. To develop balance skills, the complex is recommended for high-rise workers, rescue workers and construction workers.

Sporty and practical. Exercises are included in training for the physical development of athletes. In each sport, the set differs depending on the need to develop explosive speed, shoulder girdle, lower extremities and jump height.

Who is suitable for gymnastics?

People who practiced gymnastics in childhood have better physical development, stronger immunity and less susceptibility to diseases of the musculoskeletal system. If necessary and indicated, therapeutic exercises should be prescribed by a doctor. To engage in professional sports, good health and permission from a pediatrician are required, a child without a certificate is not allowed to practice; Therefore, before making a decision, you should learn about indications and contraindications, possible benefits and harms to the body, and consult your doctor. Gymnasts can boast of ideal posture, flexible, easy and flexible movements, strong muscles. Immunity increases, children get sick less often. Strenuous training that requires concentration and total dedication develops character, discipline to perfection, develops willpower, attention, memory and self-confidence. At the same time, children's creativity increases, they develop an ear for music and a sense of rhythm.

What are the benefits of gymnastics?

1. Strengthens muscles.
2. Supports stretching.
3. Complex apparatus exercises improve the vestibular apparatus, as well as coordination and accuracy of movements.
4. The body becomes more elastic, freedom of movement increases.
5. Increases and strengthens immunity, children suffer less from respiratory diseases.

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6. flight, the body becomes stronger in general, wounds heal faster, bones heal faster when damaged.

7. Children can carry loads better, they are able to help a lot in agriculture, gardening and other work that requires physical strength. But children who go to gymnastics every day are excluded from anything other than gymnastics - this is the other side of the coin.

8. Studying choreographic compositions improves not only plasticity, but also the musical ear. Surprisingly, gymnasts make excellent musicians, even violinists, if you have the time and desire to study at a music school at the same time.

9. Practice and communication skills can be useful in different situations, but in general, athletes feel confident in difficult situations. Children's gymnasts are leaders in physical education classes at school and have a great reputation among children, which helps to solve controversial situations at school without using physical pressure. However, a stronger person can be conflicted and this can backfire - we must not forget that for any strong person, there is always a stronger,

10. Gymnastics helps in difficult cases of treatment of various diseases, for example, rehabilitation with the help of gymnastics is carried out after a compression fracture. Gymnastics also helps when a child's growth slows down. Contrary to the belief that rhythmic gymnastics helps children grow, the high number of short children in gymnastics is due to the fact that the genetically short children are left with other activities for the taller ones. related to the transition to classes.

Summary

Gymnastics is an effective means of comprehensively developing the personality of schoolchildren, their movement abilities, and increasing the level of physical fitness with the help of physical exercises. Sports and health gymnastics complexes that have a significant effect on the activity of various systems of the human body affect the improvement of the physical and emotional state of the participants. Sports gymnastics plays an important role in the development of physical skills, improvement of aesthetic and technical abilities, and formation of a healthy lifestyle in physical education classes. In the educational process, sports gymnastics develops a healthy lifestyle among students, increases mental stability,

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develops group work, and increases the level of motivation. Therefore, the role of sports gymnastics in physical education classes and its influence on the educational process is very large. Sports gymnastics plays an important role in physical education classes and contributes greatly to the physical, mental and social development of students. Sports gymnastics helps to teach students a healthy lifestyle, to strengthen their physical and mental health, to develop their creative abilities and to form teamwork skills.

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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